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SYNERGY “SCHOOL + UNIVERSITY”: SELECTIVE MODULE “TECHNOLOGIES OF THE FUTURE”

GELMANOVA ZOYA SALIKHOVNA

Professor, Karaganda Industrial University, Temirtau, Kazakhstan

FAYEZ WAZANI ABDUL WALID

Master, Karaganda Industrial University, Temirtau, Kazakhstan

SAULSKY YURI NIKOLAEVICH

Master, Karaganda Industrial University, Temirtau, Kazakhstan

PETROVSKAYA ASIA STANISLAVOVNA

Master, Karaganda Industrial University, Temirtau, Kazakhstan

SAULSKAYA OLGA ANATOLIEVNA

Teacher, school No. 11, Temirtau, Kazakhstan

Abstract. *The modern educational environment is entering a phase when basic academic disciplines are no longer sufficient to form generations capable of not only adapting but also managing global change processes. In the context of the rapid development of bioengineering, agricultural technology, genetic engineering, energy of the future and programming, there is a need to create flexible educational modules that will allow schoolchildren of the early pre-university level to touch the technologies of tomorrow. The elective module "Future Technologies" within the Synergy "School + University" program is an innovative format for integrating research, engineering and digital education into the school-university trajectory. Unlike the basic modules focused on metacompetences (critical thinking, soft skills, leadership), this module is optional and is designed for motivated schoolchildren ready for research. This makes it a kind of "educational laboratory" - a space for trying out ideas, modeling technologies and creating prototypes. The scientific novelty of the module lies in the fact that for the first time it offers a comprehensive solution for early career guidance in STEM areas in the logic of "school + university". The methodological innovation consists of a combination of project work, mentoring of students in technical specialties and digital support (online simulations, chatbots, digital portfolios, artificial intelligence for progress analysis). This creates conditions for personalized learning, where each student gets the opportunity to build their own research trajectory.*

Keywords: *synergy school + university; elective module; bioengineering; hydroponics; genetic engineering; energy of the future; programming; research projects; educational innovations.*

The modern education system faces a double challenge: on the one hand, it is necessary to provide schoolchildren with fundamental knowledge, and on the other hand, to form readiness for life and work in the conditions of accelerated scientific and technological revolution. The development of bioengineering, genetic engineering, sustainable agricultural technologies, renewable energy and programming changes the idea of what competencies will be in demand in the coming decades. In this situation, traditional school programs are insufficient to prepare young people for the knowledge economy and innovative society [4,9-12,16-21,23-26].

The Synergy "School + University" program was developed as a response to the gap between school and university education. At the first stages, it focused on the formation of metacompetencies (critical thinking, leadership, financial literacy, soft skills), then expanded by introducing innovative modules such as Mini-MBA and student mentoring. These elements allowed us to create a solid foundation that ensures successful adaptation of schoolchildren to the university environment and the

development of management and social skills. [4-7,9-12,16-20]. The next logical step is to create an optional, selective module "Future Technologies" aimed at schoolchildren with a clear interest in STEM areas. Its peculiarity is that it is not mandatory for all participants, but works as an individual educational trajectory for motivated students who want to explore promising areas of science and technology. This format allows for a balance between mass synergetic training and in-depth research training.

Within the framework of this module, schoolchildren have the opportunity to: get in touch with bio- and genetic engineering through adapted simulations and discussions about the ethics of science; get acquainted with hydroponics and agricultural technologies as a model of sustainable development and a "green economy"; explore the energy of the future, modeling solutions for regional and global energy; master the basics of programming, which is becoming a universal tool for work in any field of science and business [21-26].

Of particular importance in this case is the participation of student mentors from technical and natural science fields, who accompany schoolchildren in research projects, explain complex terms in accessible language, and help to structure project assignments. This ensures intergenerational continuity and turns the module into a platform for interaction between schoolchildren and students on an equal footing.

Thus, the introduction of the optional module "Future Technologies" expands the educational architecture of "Synergy", combining fundamental metacompetences, management skills (Mini-MBA) and mentoring with a focus on the latest technological trends. This makes the program more flexible and innovative, providing Kazakhstan with the training of future researchers, engineers and entrepreneurs capable of solving the problems of sustainable development and global competition [4,6,7,9-12].

Bio and genetic engineering are one of the most dynamically developing areas of science, which shapes the future of medicine, agriculture and ecology. For the school-university model Synergy "school + university", the integration of these areas into the educational trajectory has a dual meaning: on the one hand, it introduces schoolchildren to current scientific achievements, and on the other, it forms their ethical and critical view of the use of technologies capable of radically changing nature and man [21,23].

Educational objectives of the block. To provide schoolchildren with basic knowledge of the principles of molecular biology and genetics in an adapted form. To introduce the possibilities and limitations of genome editing technologies. To form an understanding that biotechnology is not only a tool, but also an ethical challenge for humanity. To develop research thinking through modeling virtual experiments [21,23].

Training formats: virtual laboratories; project assignments; mentoring of biology students [21,23].

Expected effects. For schoolchildren: development of scientific interest, formation of critical thinking, familiarization with current world research, increased motivation to enroll in biotechnology and medical specialties. For student mentors: strengthening pedagogical competencies, the ability to adapt complex material for a younger audience, development of soft skills in scientific communication. For the university and the region: training potential applicants in the field of bioengineering and medicine, formation of the image of an educational environment open to innovations [4,7,9-12,21,23].

Bio- and genetic engineering block into the elective module "Future Technologies" allows schoolchildren not only to become familiar with advanced scientific trends, but also to develop a critical and value-based attitude towards them. This turns learning into a process of not passive assimilation of facts, but active reflection on how technologies affect people, society and the planet [21,23].

Hydroponics is one of the most promising technologies in the field of agriculture, which allows growing plants without using soil, using nutrient solutions instead. In the context of global climate change, population growth and limited natural resources, hydroponic systems are becoming a key

area of sustainable agriculture. The introduction of this block into the elective module "Future Technologies" gives schoolchildren a unique opportunity to come into contact with a practice that is at the intersection of biology, engineering and ecology [21-23].

Educational objectives of the block. To introduce schoolchildren to the principles of hydroponics and modern methods of agricultural technology. To show the advantages of sustainable farming: water savings, reduced use of fertilizers and pesticides, the possibility of growing in urban conditions. To develop students' design and experimental work skills through the creation of mini-installations. To cultivate environmental responsibility and understanding of the role of innovative technologies in ensuring food security [4.9-12.22].

Training formats: workshop "Mini-hydroponic installation"; research project; team assignments with mentors; discussions on sustainable development [22]:

Expected effects. For schoolchildren: practical experience in design, understanding of the principles of sustainable agriculture, increased interest in biology and engineering. For student mentors: development of research project facilitation skills, consolidation of knowledge in the field of agricultural technology, ability to explain complex processes in simple language. For the university and the region: formation of a personnel reserve for the agro-industrial complex, popularization of innovative agricultural technologies among young people. [4,9-12,21,23].

Hydroponics in the educational module "Technologies of the Future" becomes not only an object of study, but also a tool for developing engineering and research thinking. This block teaches schoolchildren to see the relationship between science and life, showing that solutions to global problems (hunger, ecology, sustainable development) begin with simple experiments and local projects [22].

Future energy is a strategic direction that determines the sustainability and competitiveness of humanity in the 21st century. The world is experiencing a transition from traditional hydrocarbon sources to renewable energy and new technological solutions - solar and wind power plants, thermonuclear reactors, smart grids, energy storage technologies and hydrogen energy. Including this block in the optional module "Future Technologies" allows schoolchildren not only to get acquainted with modern trends, but also to see the connection between global challenges and local opportunities in their region [8,13,23-25].

Educational objectives of the block. To give schoolchildren an idea of the principles of operation of renewable energy sources. To show the role of future energy in solving the problems of climate change and sustainable development. To develop an understanding of the concept of "smart grids" and digital management of energy systems. To develop skills in modeling energy solutions through design and digital tools [23-25].

Training formats: interactive simulations; mini- projects; mentoring of students of technical fields; discussion clubs. Expected effects. For schoolchildren: understanding of the global energy agenda, skills in resource analysis and design of energy solutions, development of ecological and engineering thinking. For student mentors: experience in popularizing energy technologies, ability to work with models and digital simulations, development of facilitation skills. For universities and the region: formation of interest in engineering and energy specialties, preparation of motivated applicants, support of strategic initiatives on "green energy" in Kazakhstan [8,13,23-25].

The "Energy of the Future" block shows schoolchildren that energy is not only "large power plants", but also a space for innovation, where digitalization, environmental friendliness and engineering solutions are intertwined. It forms in schoolchildren the idea that the future of energy is associated with sustainable development, digital technologies and global responsibility, which means that each of them can contribute to building an environmentally safe world [4,9-12,23-25].

Programming today is not only a tool for working in the IT sphere, but also a universal language of the modern world, which is "spoken" by science, engineering, economics and social practices. Knowledge of it allows creating digital products, managing systems, analyzing data and modeling processes. For schoolchildren of the optional module "Technologies of the Future", programming

becomes a key connecting element, allowing to combine blocks on bioengineering, hydroponics and energy into a single digital educational environment [21-26].

Educational objectives of the block. To introduce schoolchildren to basic programming languages (Python, JavaScript) and their application. To develop an understanding that programming is not only “code”, but also the logic of problem solving. To demonstrate the capabilities of digital technologies for modeling, analysis and visualization in projects on biology, agricultural technology and energy. To develop skills in working with algorithms, digital platforms and the simplest elements of artificial intelligence. [21,23-26].

Training formats: interactive workshops; mini- projects; coding marathons (mini-hackathons):

Expected effects. For schoolchildren: development of algorithmic and critical thinking; experience of integrating digital tools into interdisciplinary projects; increased confidence in working with IT technologies and awareness of their versatility. For student mentors: consolidation of programming skills through teaching; development of soft skills - the ability to explain code "in simple terms"; expansion of the portfolio through participation in mentoring digital projects. For universities and the region: preparation of schoolchildren for applicant trajectories in IT and engineering specialties; formation of an ecosystem of digital literacy among young people; contribution to the implementation of the national agenda for the digitalization of Kazakhstan [7,24,25,26].

Programming and digital technologies become the core of the module’s interdisciplinary nature: they link together biological, engineering and energy projects, turning ideas into working digital solutions. For schoolchildren, this is not only mastering the “language of the future,” but also understanding that through code they can influence reality — from a school project to global innovations [4,9-12,21,23-26].

The elective module "*Future Technologies*" is conceived as an optional educational track within the *Synergy "school + university" program*. Its difference from the basic blocks is that it is not aimed at all participants, but at motivated schoolchildren who are ready to go beyond the standard curriculum and try themselves in research and engineering practices. This format creates conditions for the formation of individual educational trajectories, and also ensures a balance between mass training and targeted support for talents.

The principle of optionality is a key feature of the elective module "Technologies of the Future", which distinguishes it from the basic mandatory blocks of the Synergy program "school + university". Unlike courses aimed at developing universal metacompetencies, this module is built on the basis of motivation and internal interest of schoolchildren. Its value lies in the fact that it includes precisely those students who strive to go beyond the standard school curriculum and immerse themselves in research activities related to advanced technologies [6,7].

Voluntary participation. Participation in the module is carried out at the student’s personal choice and does not affect his basic academic workload. This model removes the stress associated with compulsory subjects and turns the learning process into a positive educational adventure rather than an additional source of stress. Voluntariness increases internal motivation: students come to the module with a desire to learn, and not because of external pressure.

Selection mechanisms. The optional nature of the module implies minimal selection, based not on academic achievement, but on demonstrated interest: motivational essays (“Why do I want to participate in the “Future Technologies” module?”); creative tasks (mini-research or small project in the STEM direction); interviews with mentors, where the student can talk about his expectations and interests. Thus, the module includes students who are ready for exploration and experimentation, regardless of whether they are “excellent” or “average” students in the traditional grading system.

Individual trajectories. Electiveness opens up the possibility of flexibly constructing individual educational trajectories. For example:

a student can choose only one block (for example, “Programming”) and focus on it; another - go through all four areas (bioengineering, hydroponics, energy, programming) and create their own

interdisciplinary project; students can work both individually and in teams, depending on the format of the tasks [21,22-26].

Significance for the pedagogical model. Voluntary participation in the module serves several purposes at once: Selection by interest: the most motivated students are involved. Development of subjectivity : schoolchildren make conscious choices, which increases the sense of responsibility for the result. Mentoring effectiveness: student mentors work with a group of students interested in development, which means the interaction becomes more productive.

The optional nature of the “Technologies of the Future” module turns it into a space of conscious choice and research freedom, where students study not because they “have to,” but because they are truly interested. This is what creates an atmosphere of enthusiasm, creativity, and innovation that distinguishes this module from traditional compulsory courses and strengthens the general model of Synergy “school + university” [4,9-12].

Project logic is the central methodological principle of the *"Future Technologies" module*. Unlike the traditional learning model, where students acquire knowledge primarily in the form of lectures, tests and assignments, here the educational process is built around practical tasks, research initiatives and collective design of solutions. This approach not only makes learning more applied, but also prepares students for the real challenges of the university and professional environment.

Basic principles of project logic. From task to solution: training is built not from theory to practice, but vice versa: students receive a problem (case, research challenge, engineering task) that needs to be solved; theory is mastered to the extent that it is necessary for the implementation of the project. Interdisciplinarity: projects combine knowledge from different fields: biology + programming (digital model of a hydroponic installation), physics + ecology (mini solar battery), ethics + genetic engineering (discussion on genome modification); students learn to synthesize knowledge, which is especially important in the era of complex problems. Teamwork: projects are carried out in small groups (4-6 people), where the following roles are distributed: leader, analyst, programmer, presenter, mediator; role rotation allows each student to try themselves in different positions, developing soft skills. Public defense of the result: each project ends with a presentation - a mini-pitch session, where students present their product, argue their solutions and answer questions; This builds confidence in public speaking and the ability to work with feedback [7,21- 26].

Examples of project formats. Research mini-project: “How to change the composition of the nutrient solution to increase the yield of a hydroponic system?” Engineering prototype: a model of a “smart home” using solar panels and sensors. Social and ethical case: a discussion about the use of CRISPR technologies in medicine and their moral boundaries. Digital solution: developing an application for monitoring plant growth or calculating the efficiency of an energy system [1,22].

The role of student mentors in project logic: help schoolchildren structure a project (from idea to implementation); provide advice on complex issues, explaining professional terms in accessible language; facilitators of team discussions, keeping the focus on the goal.

Educational effects. For schoolchildren: development of critical and engineering thinking, ability to work in conditions of uncertainty, formation of communication skills. For student mentors: practicing project management and pedagogical facilitation techniques . For the university: creating a base for future research laboratories and start-ups with the participation of motivated applicants.

Project logic transforms the optional module “Future Technologies” into a laboratory of practical experience, where schoolchildren learn not only to assimilate knowledge, but to apply it to create specific solutions. This approach forms the thinking of the participants as a researcher and a practitioner at the same time, which corresponds to the challenges of the digital age and the principles of innovative education [4,9-12,16-20].

An important feature of the selective module *"Technologies of the Future"* is the active participation of university students in the role of mentors, tutors and facilitators . Unlike teachers, who often perform the function of knowledge translators and controllers of material assimilation, student mentors become partners of schoolchildren in the research process, which strengthens the horizontal "peer-to-peer" model and gives educational interaction the dynamics of trust and openness.

Functions of student mentors. Educational support: explaining complex scientific and technical concepts in an accessible language; assistance in mastering digital tools (simulators, laboratories, software environments); consulting schoolchildren when completing mini-projects. Facilitation of teamwork: organizing project discussions and distributing roles in groups; supporting the rotation process of leaders and participants; supporting teams in resolving conflict situations. Motivation and inspiration: demonstrating personal experience: how the student chose the direction, what projects he or she implemented; forming an image of the “near future” — schoolchildren see that in a few years they can be in the same position; creating an atmosphere of trust and partnership, unavailable in the classic “teacher-student” interaction. Developing schoolchildren’s soft skills: training communication skills through dialogues and discussions; developing empathy and the ability to argue a position; supporting in public speaking (rehearsals of pitch sessions, feedback on presentations) [7].

The effects of mentoring on the students themselves. Leadership and pedagogical empathy: students learn to lead and listen to their junior colleagues. Reinforcing professional knowledge: by explaining complex material in simple terms, mentors learn it more deeply themselves. Developing facilitation skills: experience in moderating discussions and managing group dynamics. Creating a digital portfolio: participation in mentoring is recorded in the system, increasing the academic and professional value of the student [5,6].

Systemic role for the university a. The university receives not only motivated applicants among schoolchildren, but also a new generation of student leaders who undergo practical training in pedagogical and mentoring interaction. This turns the university into a platform for multi-level educational interaction, where students not only study, but also become active subjects of the educational process.

Student mentors in the *Future Technologies module* act as catalysts for educational synergy, connecting university knowledge and schoolchildren’s motivation. Their participation makes learning less formal, more lively and closer to real practice. Mentoring becomes not only a support tool, but also a social technology for the formation of a culture of mutual assistance and continuity of generations.

Digital support for the elective module "*Future Technologies*" organically continues the architecture already tested in the previous stages of the *Synergy "school + university" program*. If in the basic level modules digital tools were used primarily for communication and progress recording (online platforms, chat bots, electronic portfolios), and in the Mini -MBA - for simulating business situations and public presentations, then in the new elective the digital environment acquires a research and engineering character, allowing schoolchildren to model real technological processes.

Key areas of digital integration. Virtual labs and simulations: develop the practice laid down in the Mini-MBA (business games, cases), but transfer it to the STEM sphere: schoolchildren can work with digital models of hydroponic systems, power plants or biological processes; create a safe space for experiments, where mistakes become part of the educational process, and not a reason for sanctions; provide access to experience that is impossible in a school lab (for example, modeling thermonuclear reactions or genome editing). Digital portfolio as an extended analogue of the MBA CV: continues the line laid down in the Mini-MBA, where each participant recorded their achievements in management and project tasks; in the "*Future Technologies*" module, the portfolio already records research and engineering practices: code solutions, mini-projects, prototypes of installations, participation in discussions on the ethics of technology; becomes an individual educational "ecosystem" reflecting the dynamics of the growth of the student's competencies. Chatbots and digital assistants: inherit the support function tested in the early *Synergy* modules: chatbots remind about tasks, help distribute roles in the project, record activity in teamwork; are supplemented with intelligent modules - a chatbot can simulate a negotiation situation, check the logic of argumentation or generate additional tasks. Artificial intelligence as a pedagogical partner: if in Mini-MBA AI acted as a simulator of business scenarios, then here it becomes a universal tool for STEM education: it simulates biological processes, analyzes energy calculations, evaluates the correctness of the program code; acts as an intelligent facilitator: suggests weak points in the project,

offers development scenarios and generates feedback in real time. Hybrid implementation model: digital infrastructure makes the module accessible to schoolchildren from different regions of Kazakhstan; project teams can work in a mixed format: offline experiments in schools are combined with online work on the university platform; This strengthens the principle of “synergy through the network”, allowing to expand the audience without losing the quality of educational interaction [1,16-25].

Educational effects of digital support. For schoolchildren: the opportunity to “try on” the role of a researcher and engineer, working with professional digital tools; increased digital literacy and confidence in STEM areas. For student mentors: developing digital facilitation skills, teaching practices through online tools, and experience integrating AI into educational processes. For universities: creating a basis for further integration of optional modules into the pre-university training system; expanding the digital infrastructure for future programs.

Digital support in the Future Technologies module is not just a technical supplement, but an innovative educational framework that ensures continuity with all previous stages of the Synergy School + University program. It combines the experience of a digital portfolio, case methods and AI simulations tested in the Mini-MBA and mentoring practices with new STEM areas, turning training into an interdisciplinary study where schoolchildren and students create the future together [1,4,9-12].

Unlike the basic modules *Synergy "school + university"* and Mini -MBA, where the "pass/fail" principle was used as a tool to relieve pressure and focus on participation, in the selective module *"Technologies of the Future"* the assessment logic requires even greater flexibility and individualization. Since participation in the module is optional, it should not turn into a source of stress control or strict certification. On the contrary, the value here is to record the educational path of each participant, emphasizing their contribution, achievements and progress.

Basic principles of evaluation. Voluntary recording of results: participation in the module does not require mandatory exams or formalized results; Students themselves choose the form in which to demonstrate their achievements: a project, a digital portfolio, an essay, a research note, or a public presentation. Multi-format: The results are recorded in different formats: digital portfolio with project records; demonstration of a prototype or simulation; participation in a mini- hackathon or research discussion; software product development;

Each format is valuable and is assessed not by strict criteria, but through quality feedback. Loyal and supportive nature: the emphasis is not on comparing participants with each other, but on individual progress; The criterion for success is not the result in absolute numbers, but the interest shown, participation and steps forward compared to one’s own starting level. Mentoring feedback: the key element of the system is feedback from student mentors and teachers; Feedback is structured in the format of “strengths – growth areas – possible steps for development,” which turns assessment into a tool for reflection rather than pressure. Self-assessment and peer assessment: students learn to analyze their own contributions and those of their team, creating a culture of open and constructive assessment; This enhances reflexivity and develops the ability to receive and give feedback.

Digital recording. All achievements are integrated into a digital portfolio, which acts not as a “report card” but as a living map of the educational path. The platform allows you to track: participation in blocks (bioengineering, hydroponics, energy, programming); completed projects and their results; feedback from mentors and self-assessment of participants; dynamics of competence development [21-26].

The assessment system in *the Future Technologies module* differs from the previous stages of Synergy by being even more individualized and flexible. There is no point in traditional assessments or ratings: the value lies in giving students space for experimentation, mistakes, and growth. Each participation is already a result, and the outcome is not a “grade in a journal,” but skills, experience, and a digital portfolio that record progress and form a sense of authorship in the student’s educational trajectory.

The implementation scenario of the optional module "*Future Technologies*" is based on the principles of flexibility, project-based approach and intergenerational mentoring. Unlike the basic program and Mini -MBA, where the educational structure is more strictly regulated, here the emphasis is on freedom of choice and variability, which allows each student to build an individual research trajectory.

Stage 1. Selection and orientation of participants.

The module starts with a motivational stage: schoolchildren submit an application in free form (essay, video presentation, mini-project), where they justify their interest in the selected topics. Introductory meetings are held with student mentors and teachers, where the objectives, structure and possibilities of the module are explained. Each student gets access to a digital platform where their educational trajectory is recorded.

Stage 2. Immersion in thematic blocks.

The module lasts one academic year and is divided into four blocks (by quarters or trimesters): Bio and genetic engineering — introduction to genetics and ethical discussions. Hydroponics and agrotechnology — creation of mini- experiments on growing plants. Energy of the future — modeling of renewable sources and smart-grid solutions. Programming and digital technologies — development of applications and simulations to support projects. Each block ends with an intermediate project: a mini-research, prototype or public defense. Students can choose one block in depth or participate in all for a broad coverage [21-26].

Stage 3. Interdisciplinary teams.

Flexible teams of schoolchildren and student mentors are formed to work on projects. In a team, schoolchildren try out different roles (leader, analyst, programmer, presenter). Role rotation builds flexible leadership and collaboration skills.

Stage 4. Digital recording and support.

All results are recorded in a digital portfolio, which becomes the main assessment tool. AI assistants offer recommendations (“develop public speaking skills,” “deepen programming knowledge”). Chatbots help schoolchildren manage deadlines and teamwork [24–26].

Stage 5. Final integration and presentation.

The academic year ends with a final pitch session, where teams present their projects, ranging from biotech concepts to energy simulators and digital solutions. The jury includes university professors, senior students, and representatives of local innovation companies. The best projects may receive support for continuation in university laboratories or business incubators [4,9-12,21,23-25].

Stage 6. Post-modular support.

Participants retain access to their digital portfolio and AI recommendations. For motivated schoolchildren, tracks of in-depth cooperation with the university are opened: participation in summer schools, internships, research circles. The university gets the opportunity for early recruitment of talented applicants.

The implementation scenario of the module "Technologies of the Future" sets a flexible, multi-level and interdisciplinary learning path, where schoolchildren do not just study new technologies, but try themselves in the role of researchers and designers. This format strengthens the continuity of the previous stages of "Synergy" (meta-competences, Mini-MBA, mentoring) and brings the program to a level where education becomes a tool for the formation of a generation of creators and innovators for Kazakhstan. [6,7,16-20].

Examples of projects in the module "Technologies of the Future" . One of the key features of the optional module is the focus on practice-oriented projects that schoolchildren develop in a team with student mentors. These projects act as "mini-laboratories of the future", where teenagers try themselves in the roles of researchers, engineers, programmers and entrepreneurs.

Bio and genetic engineering. The Virtual CRISPR Lab project: schoolchildren use digital simulation to “edit” plant DNA to increase its resistance to drought. Essay-discussion “The Ethics of Genome Editing”: teamwork on the pros and cons of using genetic engineering in medicine. Mini-

study “GMO: Myths and Reality”: schoolchildren conduct a survey at school and analyze public opinion on genetically modified products [21, 23].

Hydroponics and agricultural technologies. The School Farm on the Windowsill project: the team constructs a simple hydroponic installation and monitors the growth of plants in different solutions. Comparative experiment "Traditional soil and hydroponics": schoolchildren record the growth rate and quality of plants, analyzing the data obtained in a digital portfolio. The City of the Future: Green Roofs and Vertical Farms initiative: development of a model of a sustainable microdistrict using hydroponic technologies [22].

Energy of the Future. The Solar Station for School project: calculating the school's energy needs and modeling the installation of solar panels. Simulation of the Energy Crisis: schoolchildren, as a team of power engineers, make decisions about the distribution of resources in the event of power outages. The Smart Home Energy study: the team designs a digital lighting and heating control system to save energy [23-25].

Programming and digital technologies. Mini-hackathon "Digital School Assistant": creating a simple chatbot for a lesson schedule or FAQ for schoolchildren. Software simulator "Plant growth": schoolchildren model how plant growth conditions change depending on the composition of the nutrient solution. Data visualization "Energy of the Future": developing an interactive map showing the share of renewable sources in the energy sector of different countries [23-26].

Interdisciplinary projects. "Green City 2035": integration of bioengineering, hydroponics, energy and programming into a single sustainable city project. "School Startup": a team develops a startup idea (for example, a vertical farm for the city or an application for monitoring energy consumption) and presents it at a pitch session. "Ethical Forum": an intergenerational discussion of schoolchildren and students about which technologies of the future carry risks and which ones bring new opportunities [21-26].

The projects of the *"Future Technologies" module* provide schoolchildren with real-life experience, where they learn not only to learn new things, but also to apply them. Each task is open-ended: it is not so much the "correct answer" that is important, but a reasoned solution, creativity, and teamwork. Thus, the projects become not an academic obligation, but a space for the formation of the students' research identity.

Hypothetical case (KarIU + school No. 11, Temirtau). The integration of the optional module "Technologies of the Future" into the educational model Synergy "school + university" logically continues the trajectory we have set. If at the first stage the emphasis was on mentoring students as a social bridge, at the second - on the structural integration of the school and university through digital technologies, at the third - on Mini-MBA as the managerial core of the program, then the optional "Technologies of the Future" forms the research dimension of synergy, allowing schoolchildren to immerse themselves in the practice of STEM areas [1].

Participant selection and preparation. Schoolchildren: participation is voluntary, which corresponds to the optionality logic inherent in the new model. Selection is based not on academic performance, but on motivation and interest in research activities. Student mentors: senior students of KarIU from the fields of biotechnology, energy, IT and agricultural engineering are involved. Their role continues the “peer to peer” line tested in previous modules, but with an emphasis on scientific and engineering support. Teachers: act as coordinators and moderators, ensuring a balance between the accessibility of the material and academic depth [21,23-25].

Implementation of educational blocks. The elective is divided into four blocks, each of which strengthens and develops the Mini-MBA practices and the mentoring model already mastered by schoolchildren: Bio and genetic engineering — expands the philosophical and ethical component previously laid down in the basic modules. Hydroponics and agricultural technology — relies on the logic of project practices and forms the skills of sustainable thinking. Energy of the future — links school projects with the global agenda (ESG, green economy), which continues the ideas of strategic thinking of the Mini-MBA. Programming and digital technologies — integrates the digital platform and AI practices laid down in the second stage of "Synergy" into the STEM context. Each block ends

with a mini-project, which is recorded in the digital portfolio and can be used as a "step" for entering a university or participating in regional competitions [8,13,21-26].

Integration and final presentation. Teams of schoolchildren and students prepare interdisciplinary projects: "Green Class of the Future", "Smart School Greenhouse", "Digital Assistant for Energy Management". The final pitch session repeats the Mini-MBA practice, but is transferred to the STEM plane, where research hypotheses, engineering prototypes and digital solutions are evaluated. The jury includes representatives of KGIU, schools and regional enterprises, which makes the module a platform not only for educational, but also for innovative and social testing of ideas [4,9-12].

Expected results. For schoolchildren: consolidation of project and research work skills, confidence in STEM areas, experience in public communication. For students: development of mentoring competence and the ability to facilitate scientific and engineering projects. For the university: attracting motivated applicants and expanding the pre-university preparation model. For the region: forming the core of a youth community ready to solve the problems of sustainable development and the digital economy. The case of "Kariu + school No. 11, Temirtau" demonstrates that the optional module "Technologies of the Future" is the fourth logical stage of the evolution of the Synergy program "school + university". It combines the experience of mentoring, digital architecture, management practices of Mini-MBA and brings synergy into the sphere of research and engineering solutions, preparing schoolchildren for the challenges of the 21st century [1].

Effects for schoolchildren. Formation of a research identity: teenagers not only acquire knowledge, but try themselves in the roles of scientists, engineers, and programmers. Mastering practical STEM competencies that cannot be obtained within the standard school curriculum. Developing knowledge integration skills: combining biology, engineering, programming, and ethics in interdisciplinary projects. Increasing motivation to enter university and a conscious choice of a future professional trajectory [21–26].

Effects for student mentors. Deepening professional knowledge through teaching practice and supporting school projects. Developing the facilitation and teaching skills needed by future leaders and managers. Enrich your digital portfolio with experience working with interdisciplinary teams. Increasing the role of students at the university as active subjects of the educational process, and not just recipients of knowledge.

Effects for universities. Creation of a channel for early recruitment of talented applicants who are already familiar with the university environment and project-based learning methods. Formation of the image of the university as a center of innovative education that works proactively. Strengthening ties with regional schools and building a sustainable "school-university-community" model. Development of the infrastructure of digital and research practices that can be scaled to other educational programs of the university [4.9-12.16-20].

Effects for the region and society. Preparing a younger generation with an engineering and research mindset, ready to engage in sustainable development projects and digitalization of the economy. Creating an ecosystem of "small innovations" where school projects can be transformed into startups and social initiatives. Strengthening the social capital of the region: a culture of mentoring, horizontal cooperation and intergenerational continuity. Potential integration of the optional module into the national strategy for modernizing education in Kazakhstan, which makes it significant not only at the school or university level, but also at the state level [4.8-13.16-20].

The module "Technologies of the Future" becomes the next evolutionary stage of the Synergy "school + university" program, taking it beyond adaptation and management competencies to the formation of a research and innovation culture of the new generation. Its effects go beyond classical pedagogy: schoolchildren become researchers, students - mentors, universities - innovation centers, and the region - a platform for the formation of the personnel reserve of the 21st century. Thus, the prospects of the module are associated not only with improving the quality of education, but also with the creation of a model of the socio-technological future of Kazakhstan, where the synergy of

generations and the integration of school and university become the basis for sustainable development [4,9-12,16-20].

The optional module "Future Technologies" is not just an additional element in the structure of the Synergy "school + university" program, but its qualitative expansion and entry into a new level. If the first four stages of the model's evolution laid the foundation - from mentoring and digital integration to Mini-MBA management practices and regional testing in Temirtau - then this module opens up a research and innovation dimension, turning school-university synergy into a full-fledged laboratory of the future [4,9-12].

This is where its strategic novelty lies: Firstly, the module elevates the educational model from the level of adaptation and management competencies to the level of technological creativity. Schoolchildren become not only consumers of knowledge, but also its co-authors, trying themselves in the roles of researchers, engineers, programmers and inventors. Secondly, the elective introduces a component of variability and flexibility into the program, removing the burden of mandatory assessment procedures and providing students with freedom of choice, independence and responsibility for their own development. Thirdly, the module strengthens intergenerational synergy: student mentors, who previously helped schoolchildren adapt, are now involved in supporting research projects, becoming a bridge between university science and the school environment. Fourthly, the digital support of the module takes the educational process beyond the classroom, creating an ecosystem where students gain access to virtual laboratories, simulations and AI assistants, and their achievements are recorded in a digital portfolio - an analogue of a professional resume [8,13].

Development prospects. The module develops interdisciplinary thinking, critical analysis and digital literacy skills in schoolchildren, ensuring readiness for STEM-focused university programs. KarIU and other universities have the opportunity to build a long-term trajectory with future applicants who come not as "passive students", but as active researchers with their own portfolio of projects. The elective strengthens the culture of mentoring and peer-to-peer cooperation, builds trust between generations and makes the university a significant social partner for the school and the region. The first rudiments of research initiatives, startups and prototypes appear through school and student projects, which can be integrated into university laboratories and business incubators. The inclusion of elective modules such as "Technologies of the Future" in the educational strategy of Kazakhstan can become part of the state program for school modernization and training of personnel for the digital economy and "green energy" [8,13,23-25].

The optional module "Technologies of the Future" secures the status of a full-fledged multi-level educational ecosystem for the Synergy "school + university" program, where a student goes through the following path: from soft adaptation (mentoring); through digital integration and modular learning logic; to management thinking (Mini-MBA); regional testing (Temirtau cases); and, finally, to research and innovation experience, which forms not just "future students", but future creators of technologies and leaders of the 21st century [1,4,9-12].

Thus, "Technologies of the Future" are becoming not an elective in the traditional sense, but the culmination of a synergetic program, its strategic expansion and a guide to the future. It is this module that opens new horizons for the school, university and society of Kazakhstan, setting the foundation for a national system of early training of researchers, engineers and entrepreneurs of the digital era [8,13].

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